

Benefiting by the Electronic Information Management at Saudi Universities as an Information Source for the University Community: A study of the Status Quo and Proposing Suggestions for Development.

(PhD Proposal)

The Investigator

Anas Hashim Alahdal

Note: This research proposal presents a preliminary vision which is adjustable, developed and changed according to the supervisor's vision.

ABSTRACT

Electronic management Systems of Saudi universities designed and developed by Information and Communication Technology Centers have played a key role in automatic administrative work. The current study aims at identifying the role of E-management and its applications in Saudi Universities, exploring the current quo of E-management systems at Saudi universities, identifying patterns of benefiting patterns from E-management systems, determining the obstacles that face the users in utilizing E-management systems and provides suggestions to improve benefiting from E-management systems. The field study will be limited to measure the benefit level of the university's community related to E-management systems. The sample of the study consists of a random sample of colleges of Saudi universities, the sample will be limited to the following categories; undergraduate students, postgraduate students, administrative staff and academic staff at Saudi faculties. The Descriptive approach will be used in this study. Data will be collected by the questionnaire, checklist, semi-structured interviews and content analysis.

Key Words; Electronic Information Management, Information Source, Saudi Universities, Electronic Government.

CHAPTER ONE - INTRODUCTION:

a- Background of the Study:

We are now living in a knowledge society whose development and growth depends mainly on the sources of electronic information and communication networks, most of its members are engaged in the production, collection, storage, processing, distribution and dissemination of information (Hashim ,2017). The issue of information, how to obtain it, to store it and to facilitate its use in the service of researchers, scholars, and workers in development institutions and sectors has become a core issue; because they constitute a national wealth similar to other natural and human resources, to its place and its effective role in achieving scientific progress and cultural development and move to the information society if it is better to develop scientific plans to benefit from information and communication technologies, and the availability of qualified and specialized human resources and aware of the value of information and its importance in the fields of science and knowledge, and national development goals(Kumar,2017).

Information systems are the heart of the administrative systems that provide it information, through which the required data

on which to make decisions are made available (Ajayi&Omirin, 2017). The vast expansion and widespread use of electronic computers of various types has led to the advancement of communication technology to support information systems to serve different administrative levels; where information systems help in integration of the administrative organization, thus, information systems have become experimental - not descriptive - an effective and influential component of any sector in the country and its development (Alter, 2015).

This explains the tendency of developed countries to pay attention to this element, and to include it in its development policy and plans; where they contribute effectively to the service of citizens through access to fast and inexpensive electronic services (Masrek et al, 2017), it also promotes the spirit of innovation and creativity for the internal processes of local government, and provides several alternatives and ways to provide the service, whether for citizens or various government agencies, so the use of information technology in government agencies has been linked to the emergence of a modern concept called e-government or e-management(Germo&Adhair,2017).

b- Problem Statement:

The digital revolution - of information and communication - that the world is witnessing now has changed many administrative concepts. Most countries have become dependent on information systems, and introducing it in most governmental and non-governmental bodies, especially in the administrative bodies that provide services to the community, under the application of

e-government (Haag et al ,2018).

With the advancement of science and knowledge, its ramifications and increasing competence, the problem of sheer volume and an increasing amount of information has emerged, and the diversity of its sources and references, the problem arose of the need to control this vast amount of information and the need to regulate it (Gwaltnet, 2017), so that it can be accessed when needed as quickly as necessary and in an appropriate manner, so the responsibility of libraries, universities and scientific research centers have been multiplied in the field of information preservation, its sources and tools, and their effective organization, in order to provide assistance to researchers and scholars and to guide them to the information they need ; As a result, there is a need for information systems that collect and process data both internally produced and derived from the external environment, and supplying this information for different administrative levels, which helps universities to develop continuously through the availability of information to their administrative leadership in all fields in a timely manner(O'Brien, 2019).

Questions of the Study:

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- Do ICT centers in Saudi universities contribute to establishing a technological environment in it?
- Do electronic management systems interact with the university community in Saudi universities?
- Does the use of electronic management systems differ from

- one category to another in the Saudi university community?
- To what extent do electronic management systems at Saudi universities help to provide accurate and timely data in order to enable management to exercise its functions?
 - Do you influence electronic management systems positively on the performance of university administration?

c- Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To highlight the role of electronic information management, and the importance of its application in universities.
- Survey of the reality of electronic management systems in Saudi universities.
- Defining patterns of utilization and use of the university community categories in Saudi universities (undergraduate students, postgraduate students, administrative staff and academic staff) for electronic management systems.
- Determining obstacles to the use of electronic management systems in colleges and units of Saudi universities.
- Providing a set of proposals aimed at improving access to electronic management systems.

Importance of the Study:

The study importance is clearing in highlighting the importance of the technological environment in university institutions, which will help the university community to fulfill its mission, and help him to obtain information; where universities and institutions seek to employ telecommunications networks and

databases in an effective manner, to achieve its objectives in education and professional and human development, this helps to transform the traditional system of government management into an IT-based system, in order to facilitate e-government performance of its public services, and to deliver them as quickly and as high as possible to the service.

Saudi universities are at the forefront of Arab and international universities that are trying to invest in modern developments; where it established ICT centers in early 1990, to build a modern technical institution to help the university to catch up with the information age. The most important achievements of these centers during the previous years are the design and construction of electronic systems in accordance with international standards, to transform all university work activities into e-performance; therefore, the current study attempts to identify the impact of electronic management systems for Saudi universities in meeting the needs of the university community.

CHAPTER TWO - REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND RELATED STUDIES:

Study (Moses, 2019) entitled "Availability, accessibility and use of information and communication technology in management of students' academic affairs in Makerere University" The study aimed to identify the availability of ICTs and use by students in academic affairs at Makerere University in Uganda to facilitate electronic records management, the data was collected through the questionnaire by interviewing students, in addition to holding group interviews with them. The study found that the availability of

Internet access facilities, computers, management information systems, and electronic databases have helped students to use various applications of the system, and easily accessible, except for entering into some subsystems of results, and correction of examinations. The study also found difficulties in the use of ICTs to register outside the university.

Study (Whitbeck, 2018) entitled "An Information system model for construction project management in University Facility Departments" This study dealt with a model information system for the management of projects in university administration facilities; information systems are a crucial tool in many areas to provide information for decision-making and support, the information system model was developed and documented using a diagramming methodology, data flow to document basic information, which must be obtained and stored in the system effectively, in addition to the information system model includes a recommended list of events , which must be undertaken in order to meet information needs from a typical university facility, the study also , included a special management information system for four projects.

Study (Abdulkareem, 2018) entitled "comparative analysis of management information systems utilization for organizational effectiveness in colleges of education in Nigeria" The study aimed to compare the impact of the management of the electronic information system on organizational effectiveness in the faculties of education in Nigeria, 1670 individuals were selected randomly, by using a stratified random sample, in 24 of the 65 colleges of education in Nigeria, the sample included 895 faculty members, 522 administrators and 253 students, the questionnaire was used

through the interview to collect field data. The study found that federal education colleges ranked first in terms of the use and management of the electronic information system, followed by regional education colleges, then colleges of education in private universities, the study also found that the MIS needs to be developed, in relation to the provision of electronic courses for students, and interaction between them and the faculty.

Study (Gwaltner , 2017) entitled" Model management information system for an institution of higher education" The study included designing a management information system model to help manage available resources and long-term planning, the study includes five models of data files (Individuals - students - graduates - facilities - financial), and dealt with the analysis of the current requirements of the system, analysis of responses to the questionnaire to identify data needs by a sample of managers in higher education institutions.

Study (Ming, 2016) entitled "Development and application of university integrated teaching affairs management information system" The study aimed to describe the potential of an integrated management information system for the management of teaching, through the Internet environment, by its ability to display information; Such as student data, academic registration, the scheduling and selection of courses for each semester, giving advice to the student from time to time, in addition to assessing the data security and information of the system, and integration and compatibility between subsystems of the system and some. The study found the importance of this system in encouraging the learning environment within the university in two directions by giving different information to the student, and allowing the faculty

member to follow up the activities of the student and communicate with him.

Study (Park, 2016) entitled "Developing a framework for authenticity requirements in university student records system" The purpose of this study is to identify the requirements to ensure that records available in electronic recordkeeping systems are correct, the researcher interviewed the system administrators, and administrators of student records systems in four academic institutions; in Canada, the United States, Korea and Australia. The results of the study indicate the similarity of the functions of the student records systems in the four universities, although systems differ in terms of design and infrastructure, and associated application programs.

Study (Su, 2015) entitled "Development and design of the employment management information system of university-based on web" The study dealt with an administrative information system for graduates aimed at obtaining accurate information from institutions and graduates in due course, and increasing the employment rate of graduates, the study addressed the main requirements for an electronic management system for graduates applied in institutions of higher education, where the technical requirements that help in the design and development of the system, the study also aimed to evaluate experimental version for system in light of the standards and specifications required in the electronic systems.

The present study has agreed, with most of the previous

studies in several aspects, as follows:

- Presentation of the conceptual framework of e-management, its importance and its applications represented in the electronic information management systems in universities and the obstacles to their use.
- Determining the technical requirements for the application of electronic information management systems in universities.
- Determining the extent of use of the categories - study sample - from the electronic information management systems applied in the universities and benefiting from them.

The current study differs from the previous studies in several aspects as follows:

- Previous studies have focused on the use and benefit of the university community of electronic information management systems in one category , while the current study deals with the benefit of all categories of the university community (undergraduate students, postgraduate students, administrative staff and academic staff) for electronic management systems.
- Previous studies have focused on one system of electronic information management systems applied in universities, especially the academic registration system for students, while the current study will study all electronic information management systems in Saudi universities.
- Previous studies have relied on the use of one main tool in data collection, whether the checklist or questionnaire, while the current study will rely on the checklist, questionnaire, interviews and content analysis as tools for collecting study data.

In general, the present study has benefited from previous studies in the methodology used, the theoretical framework planning, the design of the study tools, and the analysis and interpretation of the

results of the study.

Conceptual Framework:

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION TO STUDY.

Introduction, study problem, study objectives, study hypothesis, study importance, terminology of the study, the limits of the study.

CHAPTER TWO: PREVIOUS STUDIES AND RELATED STUDIES.

E-MANAGEMENT AND ITS APPLICATIONS IN THE UNIVERSITIES

CHAPTER THREE: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

- E-management and its applications in the universities.
- E-Management Systems of Saudi universities.
- Benefit level of the academic staff from E-Management Systems.
- Benefit level of the students from E-Management Systems.
- Benefit level of the administrative staff from E-Management Systems.

CHAPTER FOUR: FIELD STUDY & METHODOLOGY

- Study Approach.
- Study Sample.
- Study Tools.
- Field Study.
- Statistical Processing Methods.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

(Figure. 1) Diagrammatic illustration of the study framework based on literature review.

CHAPTER THREE - THE STUDY METHODOLOGY:

a- Study Design:

The current study aims at identifying the role of electronic information management and its applications in Saudi Universities, exploring the current quo of E-management systems at Saudi universities, identifying patterns of benefiting patterns from E-management systems, determining the obstacles that face the users in utilizing E-management systems and provides suggestions to improve benefiting from electronic information management systems. This research will be a mixed-method research and will adopt a descriptive survey design in collecting information by administering questionnaires to a sample of the target population. The study will be aimed at collecting information from the respondents, regarding the benefit level of the university's community related to electronic information management systems , thus, the study will rely on the descriptive approach as the most suitable for dealing with the reality of the electronic information management systems in the Saudi universities and analyzing them, and studying the extent of benefit faculty members, their assistants, students and administrators from E-management systems. The investigator will use both the primary and the secondary data. Primary data will be obtained using questionnaires while secondary data will be found from books, journals, and The Internet.

b- Study Sample:

The study sample will include three categories:

- (1) **Academic Staff & their assistants:** The sample of the study will be chosen in a random stratified manner, where representing the academic grades and the different scientific disciplines in the faculties of Saudi universities.
- (2) **Undergraduate students & Postgraduate students:** The sample of the study will be chosen for this category in a random stratified manner, representing the scientific departments and the different levels in the faculties of Saudi universities, according to the statistical bulletin of the university.
- (3) **Administrative Staff:** The study sample will be selected for this category in a regular random method, from departments dealing with electronic management systems, namely; student affairs, graduate studies, personnel affairs (general - special), library, and graduates affairs at colleges of Saudi universities.

To determine the sample size of the study- in each category - the researcher uses Stephen Thon

$$n = \frac{N \times p(1-p)}{\lceil N - 1 \times (d^2 \div z^2) + p(1-p) \rceil}$$

c- Data Collection and Instruments:

The main data collection instruments to be used include the following:

1. Survey questionnaires:

Survey Questionnaires have an advantage of achieving rapid contact with many people. It will be very useful for this research

project to obtain responses to the diverse indicators requiring consultations with specific populations. (Undergraduate students, postgraduate students, administrative staff and academic staff at Saudi faculties).

A questionnaire will be prepared that will include a set of questions covering all areas of the study and achieving its objectives for each category of the study sample. Through several steps to build the questionnaire and prepare it in its final form as follows:

- Studying previous studies questionnaires on the subject of electronic information management.

- Use all sources of information available on electronic management systems to build the questionnaire.

- Formulation of the questionnaire items from open questions and closed questions, and then arbitration of the questionnaire in its initial form by faculty members and arbitrators in the specialization.

- Reviewing and implementing the observations and amendments of the arbitrators.

- Procedure the pre-test questionnaire by applied it 10 individuals in each category.

- Modification of the formulation of some questions in the questionnaire based on the results of the initial test, and then the questionnaire will be distributed to the categories of the study sample

2. Semi-Structured Interviews:

The interview procedure is a shedding light on research process through an informal conversation. As part of this research project, an interview guide will be drawn to make the interviews semi-structured. Interview questions will be written down, and the interviewers will be trained so that they truly understand the subject matter as well the responses they receive. In the current study, an interview will be conducted with the officials of the electronic management systems at the ICT centers at the faculties of Saudi universities.

3. Checklist: The researcher will prepare a checklist to conduct a detailed study of each electronic information management system at the faculties of Saudi universities to determine their current status.

4. Content Analysis: The researcher will analyze the content of electronic information management systems in the colleges and the representative bodies of the study sample.

5. A Compendium of Textual Data: will primarily gather, organize and analyze diverse documents that contain relevant information to the topic of study for example electronic information management databases and manuals for various systems.

d- Data analysis Methods:

The researcher will use the appropriate statistical treatments for the study objectives through the (SPSS ver 22) program. The researcher will use the following statistical methods:

- **Alpha correlation coefficient:** To calculate the reliability and

validity of the survey list items.

- **Arithmetic Mean:** To determine the relative importance of the responses of the three categories of the study sample, with regard to variables in the survey list and it reflects at proposing suggestions for development.

- **Standard Deviation:** To measure the degree of dispersion in the opinions of the three categories of the study sample, with regard to the items in the survey list.

- **Mann Whitney Test:** To find the differences between the trends of the members of the three categories of the study sample.

-Pearson Correlation Coefficient: To study the degree of correlation between the components of proposing suggestions for development.

In addition to the previous statistical methods, the researcher will use Frequencies, Percentages, Weighted Average, and Chi-square Test as tools for analyzing study data and presenting final results.

e- Mechanisms to Assure Quality of the Study:

Control of Bias: the researcher will make sure that the research study is objective, independent and balanced. The researcher believes that objectivity is critical to the success of scientific analysis. Thus, the researcher will actively work to keep a neutral and objective research environment.

Use accurate and most reliable data: To assure that the research study is useful, informative and understandable data and information of the best quality will be used. The data and information used in the research study will be validated from multiple sources and it will be assured that it is reliable and

accurate.

f- Research Study Period:

The proposed research study will be completed in three years.

	YEAR ONE				YEAR TWO				YEAR THREE			
	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec
Literature review	[Orange bar]											
Research proposal	[Dark Blue bar]											
Development of tools					[Green bar]							
Data collection					[Light Blue bar]				[Light Blue bar]			
Analysis of Data					[Dark Red bar]							
Thesis write-up					[Yellow bar]				[Yellow bar]			
Thesis Submission												[Purple bar]

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